

Characterizing modal noise in high-resolution échelle spectra using flat-field images

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ABSTRACT

Modal noise, the wavelength-dependent flux modulation caused by interference between propagation modes in an optical fiber, remains a limiting factor for the long-term stability of fiber-fed, high-resolution échelle spectrographs that aim for extreme radial-velocity (RV) precision. We present a flat-field-based method to quantify the spatial-frequency content and temporal evolution of modal noise, applied to five fibers spanning the multimode, few-mode, and single-mode regimes at the Waltz échelle spectrograph ($R \approx 65\,000$) at the Landessternwarte, Heidelberg. Hour-long time series of normalized, per-order flat-field spectra are reorganized into single-order time-series (SOTS) images that directly visualize wavelength- and time-dependent flux fluctuations, and are further characterized through per-order Fourier transforms and shot-noise-subtracted statistics. For one representative fiber per mode regime – a large-core multimode, a few-mode, and a single-mode fiber – we find peak-to-valley flux modulations ranging from below 1% (multimode and single-mode) to about 8% (few-mode), with the few-mode fiber alone showing strong, structured, order-dependent Fourier signatures characteristic of discrete mode interference, while the single-mode fiber is statistically indistinguishable from pure shot noise. These results confirm that modal noise severity scales with the number of supported modes and that SOTS and per-order Fourier analysis provide a sensitive hardware-light diagnostic for modal noise, directly relevant to the fiber-feed design choices of next-generation high-precision spectrographs such as 2ES, MARVEL, and ANDES-K.

Keywords: modal noise, fiber optics, échelle spectrograph, radial velocity, flat-field calibration, Fourier analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

The search for Earth-like exoplanets via the radial-velocity (RV) method is pushing high-resolution échelle spectrographs toward unprecedented long-term stability, with current and next-generation instruments targeting RV precisions at the 1 m/s and 10 cm/s level or below (e.g. 2ES,¹ MARVEL,² and ANDES³). Coupling the telescope beam with the spectrograph through an optical fiber is now standard practice, since the fiber mechanically decouples the instrument from the telescope and homogenizes (“scrambles”) the illumination pattern at the spectrograph entrance, suppressing fluctuations caused by guiding errors and seeing.⁴

This benefit comes at a cost. Light propagating through a multimode fiber distributes itself among a finite number of discrete propagation modes, whose mutual interference produces a speckle-like intensity pattern in the near- and far-field outputs of the fiber. Wherever a downstream optical element clips, vignettes, or otherwise discriminates against parts of this speckle pattern (as is generally the case in a spectrograph slit, grating, or detector), the result is a wavelength- and time-dependent flux modulation known as modal noise.⁵ Unlike fixed-pattern noise, modal noise evolves with the modal content of the illumination and cannot be removed by standard flat-fielding; instead it appears as excess noise on the extracted spectrum, shifting measured line centroids, and

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ultimately limiting the achievable RV precision.^{6–8} Its severity is governed primarily by the number of modes a fiber supports: many-mode (large-core, high-NA multimode) fibers produce a dense, fast-averaging speckle pattern and comparatively stable illumination, while few-mode fibers support only a handful of high-contrast speckles whose motion, e.g. under mechanical or thermal perturbation, causes large excursions in coupled flux. Single-mode fibers, which support no interference modes, are intrinsically free of modal noise, at the cost of strongly reduced throughput for an extended source.

Mechanical agitation of the fiber, which randomizes the modal content on a timescale shorter than the exposure, is an established and effective mitigation strategy,⁹ but it does not eliminate modal noise entirely, particularly for few-mode fibers. This is of direct relevance to the Landessternwarte (LSW) instrumentation group’s involvement in several next-generation, ultra-stable spectrograph projects, including 2ES (targeting 10 cm/s precision),¹ MARVEL, and the K-band module of ANDES (ANDES-K).³ Near-infrared operation in ANDES-K in particular favors small fiber cores to minimize thermal background, which inevitably reduces the number of supported modes and raises the risk of significant modal noise – motivating a systematic, quantitative study of how modal noise scales with mode count.

In this paper we present a flat-field-based method for characterizing modal noise that requires no on-sky data: hour-long time series of spectral flat-field exposures are used to build single-order time-series (SOTS) images and per-order Fourier spectra that directly visualize and quantify modal noise as a function of wavelength, time, and spatial frequency. We apply this method to five fibers spanning the multimode, few-mode, and single-mode regimes at the Waltz échelle spectrograph at the LSW, and use one representative fiber per regime to establish how modal noise severity, spatial structure, and temporal behavior scale with the number of supported modes. Section 2 describes the instrument, fiber set, and observations; Section 3 details the analysis methods; results are presented in Section 4 and discussed in Section 5.

2. INSTRUMENT, FIBERS, AND OBSERVATIONS

All measurements were carried out at the Waltz échelle spectrograph¹⁰ at the Landessternwarte, Heidelberg, a fiber-fed instrument with a resolving power of $R \approx 65\,000$ and a nominal wavelength range of 450–800 nm spread over about 50 échelle orders. The reddest orders are dominated by detector and background noise and are excluded from this analysis, leaving an effective range of about 450–750 nm.

Five fibers were tested, spanning the multimode, few-mode, and single-mode regimes (Table 1). Two of these – a 100 μm -core multimode fiber (“C100”) and an 8.2 μm -core few-mode fiber (“28E”, Thorlabs 28E10) – together with a single-mode fiber of core diameter below 2 μm (“460B”, Thorlabs M460B) are used as representative examples of their respective mode regimes throughout Section 4. Light from a Thorlabs MCWHL5 white-light LED was injected into each fiber with an $F/3$ beam and a ~ 10 μm focal spot, centered on and overfilling the fiber core, in order to robustly excite all supported modes. Each fiber could optionally be mechanically agitated (~ 0.5 Hz, ~ 10 cm stroke) to randomize its modal content on a timescale shorter than the exposure time, a standard modal noise mitigation strategy;⁹ for the time-series analysis presented here the fiber was instead held static, in order to isolate the intrinsic, mode-count-dependent modal noise signature without the averaging effect of agitation. Two coupling configurations were used: an *indirect* configuration, in which the fiber under test fed a 33×132 μm fiber identical to the one normally used to feed the spectrograph from the telescope, and a *direct* configuration, in which the fiber under test was coupled straight into the spectrograph slit. All results shown in Section 4 are for the direct configuration.

For each fiber, a time series of 60 flat-field exposures was recorded at a cadence of one exposure per minute, for a total duration of about one hour, following the approach of Oliva et al.¹¹ This sampling rate is fast compared to the timescale of typical RV-relevant calibration cadences, but slow enough to be dominated by mechanical and thermal drifts of the unagitated fiber and lab environment rather than by detector noise, making it well suited to revealing the slow, structured flux variations characteristic of modal noise.

Table 1. Fibers tested in this work. Mode regime follows from the fiber V-number ($V = \pi d \text{NA}/\lambda$); multimode fibers support $M \approx V^2/2$ modes, while fibers with $V \lesssim 2.405$ support a single mode.

Designation	Core diameter	NA	Mode regime
C-100	100 μm	0.22	Multimode
C-18	18 μm	0.22	Multimode
M64L02	10 μm	0.10	Few-mode
28E10 (“28E”)	8.2 μm	0.14	Few-mode
M460B (“460B”)	< 2 μm	0.10–0.14	Single-mode

3. ANALYSIS METHODS

3.1 Normalization

Each raw flat-field image is dark-subtracted and its échelle orders extracted and collapsed along the cross-dispersion direction, yielding one 2048-pixel row per order and a 50×2048 -pixel image per exposure (order number vs. dispersion pixel/wavelength). For each fiber, a mean image is computed by averaging all ~ 60 exposures of the time series, and every individual exposure is divided by this mean. This removes the blaze function and the spectral shape of the lamp, which are constant in time, and leaves a normalized image centered on unity that isolates time-variable structure, i.e. modal noise.

3.2 SOTS images and noise statistics

To inspect the time evolution of a single order in isolation, the normalized images are re-sliced so that each row is the same order taken from one exposure of the time series, with rows stacked in time order; we refer to the resulting images as single-order time-series (SOTS) images. A “wide” variant of this format retains a few pixels of cross-dispersion information per order instead of fully collapsing it, allowing spatial structure across the slit image to be inspected as well.

For each SOTS image, the distribution of normalized pixel values is fit with a Gaussian, whose standard deviation σ_{fit} is taken as the total measured noise; we also compute a 2nd-to-98th-percentile peak-to-valley statistic as a robust measure of the noise amplitude. A shot-noise model is computed independently from the non-normalized counts, $\sigma_{\text{shot}} = \sqrt{N}/g$, with N the number of counts and $g = 1.2$ the gain of the Waltz CCD. The shot-noise-subtracted residual noise,

$$\sigma_{\text{res}} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{fit}}^2 - \sigma_{\text{shot}}^2}, \quad (1)$$

then isolates the noise contribution in excess of shot noise, which we attribute to modal noise.

3.3 Per-order Fourier analysis

To characterize the spatial-frequency content of modal noise, we Fourier-transform the normalized, collapsed order stripes along the dispersion direction using the fast Fourier transform (FFT), producing one Fourier spectrum per order per exposure. Stacking these by order yields a single image per exposure (order vs. spatial frequency); these are then mean-combined over the full time series to boost signal-to-noise and yield one representative per-order Fourier image per fiber, analogous to the per-order, time-averaged Fourier approach of Oliva et al.¹¹ This representation directly reveals whether modal noise power is broadband or concentrated at specific spatial frequencies, and whether its spatial signature depends on échelle order (i.e. on wavelength).

4. RESULTS

4.1 Visual appearance of SOTS images

Figure 1 shows SOTS images of the same échelle order (order 26, $\lambda \approx 5698\text{--}5710 \text{ \AA}$) for the three representative fibers, each built from 60 exposures spaced one minute apart. The three fibers are immediately visually distinguishable. The multimode C100 fiber shows low-amplitude noise structures with only slight temporal variation. The few-mode 28E fiber shows high-amplitude noise structures with strong, comparably fast temporal variation.

The single-mode 460B fiber shows no discernible structure at all: Its SOTS image is consistent with pure random (shot) noise and has no temporal dependence. This visual progression already illustrates the central result of this work: modal noise amplitude and temporal variability both increase sharply as the number of supported modes decreases from multimode to few-mode, and vanish once the fiber is single-mode.

Figure 1. SOTS images for the three representative fibers (order 26, $\lambda \approx 5698\text{--}5710 \text{ \AA}$, 60 exposures at one-minute cadence). Each panel shows the same order over the full time series; wavelength runs horizontally, time runs vertically.

4.2 Noise statistics and mode-count scaling

Figure 2 shows the per-order noise statistics for the three representative fibers, which confirm the qualitative picture from the SOTS images. For the few-mode 28E fiber, residual noise is highest and most unstable from order to order, typically exceeding 1% and rising toward the red; here, residual noise dominates the total measured noise. For the multimode and single-mode fibers, residual noise is comparable in magnitude (typically a few tenths of a percent) and only mildly in excess of shot noise across most of the wavelength range; even for the single-mode 460B fiber, where modal interference cannot occur, a small non-zero residual remains, which we attribute to a minor non-modal noise contribution rather than to modal noise. In terms of the 2nd-to-98th-percentile peak-to-valley statistic, this translates into peak-to-valley flux modulations below 1% for the multimode and single-mode fibers and around 8% for the few-mode fibers (Table 2), consistent with the ~ 4000 , ~ 50 , and 1 supported modes estimated for the C100, 28E, and 460B fibers, respectively, from their V-numbers.

Table 2. Summary of results for the three representative fibers (direct coupling, static fiber, central overfilled injection).

Fiber	Mode regime	Modes (approx.)	Modal noise severity	Peak-to-valley
C100	Multimode	~ 4000	Low	$< 1\%$
28E	Few-mode	~ 50	High	$\sim 8\%$
460B	Single-mode	1	None	$\approx 0\%$

Figure 2. Per-order noise statistics for the three representative fibers (direct coupling, static fiber): Total noise from a Gaussian fit (blue), the modeled shot-noise floor (orange), and the shot-noise-subtracted residual attributed to modal noise (green), as a function of échelle order.

4.3 Fourier signatures

Figure 3 shows the mean-combined, per-order Fourier transforms for the three representative fibers. The single-mode 460B fiber is essentially featureless and shot-noise dominated across all orders, as expected for a fiber with no interfering modes. The multimode C100 fiber is similarly smooth except for a single, isolated low-spatial-frequency feature that is present at essentially the same frequency in every order, widening slightly toward the red. The few-mode 28E fiber, in contrast, shows strong, highly structured Fourier power that varies markedly from order to order. This is a signature of discrete, order-dependent mode interference that is qualitatively distinct from the smooth, low-amplitude behavior of the other two fibers.

Figure 3. Mean-combined per-order Fourier transforms for the three representative fibers. Each row is the Fourier transform of one échelle order, computed along the dispersion direction and averaged over the full time series.

4.4 Wavelength dependence and temporal behavior

Within the effective wavelength range used here, both the residual-noise statistics and the Fourier signatures show a degree of dependence on échelle order (i.e. Wavelength). For the multimode and single-mode fibers, residual noise follows a shallow U-shape across the order range (See Figure 2), rising toward both the bluest and reddest orders used and reaching a minimum near the middle of the range; this is consistent with shot noise dominating more strongly toward the edges of the effective wavelength range, where flux from the white-light source is lowest. The few-mode fiber’s residual noise is comparatively flat across most of the range but rises sharply toward the reddest orders. This pattern is echoed in the Fourier signatures (Figure 3): The few-mode fiber’s discrete interference features vary strongly and continuously with order, the multimode fiber’s single low-frequency feature widens slightly toward the red, and the single-mode fiber’s Fourier spectrum remains essentially flat and featureless across all orders, consistent with its lack of modal noise. Temporally, the single-mode fiber shows no time dependence at all, also consistent with its lack of modal noise. The few-mode fiber shows the most rapid and unstable temporal variation, whereas the multimode fiber shows slower, larger-scale temporal structure. Here, the flux in a given order completes multiple full peak-to-valley cycles over the one-hour time series, suggesting a slow, possibly mechanical or thermal, drift of the residual modal pattern rather than a fast stochastic process.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

These results demonstrate that modal noise, as measured through hour-long flat-field time series, scales strongly with the number of modes a fiber supports: Peak-to-valley flux modulations of less than 1% for the multimode and single-mode fibers tested here rise to about 8% for the few-mode fiber, with the few-mode case further distinguished by strong, order-dependent Fourier signatures and rapid, unstable temporal variation that are absent in the other two regimes. The single-mode fiber is statistically consistent with the shot-noise limit, confirming that it is intrinsically free of modal noise, while the large-core multimode fiber approaches this limit closely despite supporting thousands of modes.

The SOTS-image and per-order Fourier techniques presented here require only flat-field exposures and no additional hardware, making them straightforward to apply to any existing fiber-fed spectrograph as an in-situ modal noise diagnostic. The fact that Fourier signatures are fiber-type-specific and highly reproducible suggests they could also be used to monitor a spectrograph's fiber feed for changes over time, e.g. after fiber replacement or reconnection.

These results are directly relevant to the fiber-feed design trade-off faced by next-generation, ultra-stable spectrographs such as 2ES,¹ MARVEL,² and ANDES-K.³ The practical relevance of these results depends critically on the coupling regime. In AO-fed systems operating at high Strehl, the PSF is already near-diffraction-limited, and a fiber core matched to this PSF will typically be single-mode or at most support a handful of modes. In that case, the cleaner choice is a single-mode fiber. The few-mode regime offers no coupling advantage and, as our results show, carries a significant modal noise penalty. In seeing-limited systems, the appropriate fiber core scales with the seeing disk and thus with telescope aperture. For large apertures ($D \gg r_0$), a seeing-matched fiber is inherently highly multimode and modal noise is manageable. It is only when the telescope aperture approaches the Fried parameter r_0 (as occurs for small telescopes or in excellent seeing conditions) that a seeing-matched fiber naturally enters the few-mode regime, and modal noise becomes a genuine concern. In that scenario, our results underline that effective mechanical agitation is essential, since the static, unagitated few-mode case studied here represents close to a worst-case for modal-noise-induced RV error.

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REFERENCES

1. J. Stürmer *et al.*, “2ES: Second Earth-Initiative Spectrograph,” in *Proc. SPIE*, **13096**, 2024.
2. G. Raskin, C. Schwab, B. Vandenbussche, J. De Ridder, C. Lanthermann, J. Pérez Padilla, A. Tkachenko, H. Sana, P. Royer, S. Prins, L. Decin, D. Defrère, J. Pember, D. Atkinson, A. Glasse, D. Pollacco, G. Tinetti, M. Güdel, J. Stürmer, I. Ribas, A. Brandeker, L. Buchhave, S. Halverson, G. Avila, J. Morren, and H. Van Winckel, “Marvel, a four-telescope array for high-precision radial-velocity monitoring,” in *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy VIII*, C. J. Evans, L. Simard, and H. Takami, eds., **11447**, p. 114471G, SPIE, 2020.
3. A. Marconi *et al.*, “ANDES, the high resolution spectrograph for the ELT,” in *Proc. SPIE*, **12184**, p. 1218424, 2022.
4. J. Baudrand and G. A. H. Walker, “Modal noise in high-resolution, fiber-fed spectra: a study and simple cure,” *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific* **113**, pp. 851–858, 2001.
5. U. Lemke, J. Corbett, J. Allington-Smith, and G. Murray, “Modal noise prediction in fibre spectroscopy—i. visibility and the coherent model,” *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* **417**(1), pp. 689–697, 2011.
6. R. T. Blackman, D. A. Fischer, C. A. Jurgenson, *et al.*, “Performance verification of the EXtreme PREcision Spectrograph,” *The Astronomical Journal* **159**, p. 238, 2020.
7. J.-F. Donati, D. Kouach, C. Moutou, *et al.*, “SPIRou: NIR velocimetry and spectropolarimetry at the CFHT,” *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* **498**, pp. 5684–5703, 2020.

8. H. R. A. Jones *et al.*, “SHREX: Small actively controlled high-resolution exoplanet spectrograph,” *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific* **133**, 2021.
9. R. R. Petersburg *et al.*, “Modal noise mitigation through fiber agitation for fiber-fed radial velocity spectrographs,” *The Astrophysical Journal* **853**, p. 181, 2018.
10. M. Tala *et al.*, “A high-resolution spectrograph for the 72 cm Waltz Telescope at Landessternwarte, Heidelberg,” in *Proc. SPIE*, **9908**, pp. 2015–2021, 2016.
11. E. Oliva, L. Origlia, C. Baffa, *et al.*, “Experimental characterization of modal noise in multimode optical fibers for the GIANO-B spectrograph,” *Astronomy & Astrophysics* **632**, p. A21, 2019.